

*Bashar Malkawi, A Bright Future: Towards an Enhanced Shariah Supervision in Islamic Finance*, THE EUROPEAN FINANCIAL REVIEW 14-16 (February/March 2014).

Independence of the Shariah Supervisory Board One aspect of independence is the way members of the Shariah Supervisory Board are paid. Members receive remuneration from the Islamic financial institution, and there exists a potential conflict of interest whereby there is an assumption of legitimising unlawful or dubious operations to ensure that they remain on the board ie acting as a rubber stamp. Even though such assumption is not truly accurate, as board members are expected to be guided by moral belief and religious values, it still needs a proper framework in the form of policy or regulation because the credibility of Islamic financial institutions depends on the perceived independence of the board. Any proposal for Board Members to avoid financial remuneration altogether, so that their opinions are not to be influenced by the Islamic financial institution, is not practical. Therefore, any regulation addressing the remuneration of Shariah Supervisory Board members must set clear guidelines on fixing the salary, bonuses, and any other nonfinancial rewards. The salary packages of Shariah scholars must be reasonable and approved by the shareholders. Also, remuneration must be linked to performance hence acting as an effective tool in attracting, motivating, and retaining scholars. As part of good corporate governance practices, disclosure of remuneration, against the total cost for the Islamic financial institution, provides a means for Shariah scholars to discharge their accountability to the Islamic financial institution, and recognises the potential conflict of interest that arises between the remuneration of Shariah scholars.